

Vol:1, Issue: 4 pp: 379-387

JEL Codes: I2, I20, I29

AYEGA D. (2020). "Integrating Mobile Learning Assessment Tools in High School Science", Vol: 1 Issue: 4 pp: 379-387

Keywords: *mobile assessment, mobile assessment tools, mobile devices, mobile learning, m-learning, chromebooks*

Article Type Review Article

Integrating Mobile Learning Assessment Tools in High School Science

Arrived Date
11.10.2020

Accepted Date
21.08.2020

Published Date
31.10.2020

Douglas Ayega*

ABSTRACT

Mobile assessment tools such as smartphones and tablets are not only used in communication and entertainment but are also useful in the assessment and instructional purposes. These device functionalities are enhanced by their capability to connect to the internet and support visual displays, text input, voice controls, and hardware and software controls such as keypads, which were traditionally limited to desktop computers. These assemblies have been customized through downloadable applications to display, monitor, self-evaluate, and track information, factors which offer significant parameters that are useful in promoting and evaluating learning. This study analyzed a variety of literature reviews on the impacts and challenges of using mobile devices in high school science and the methodologies that were employed in these studies. It also scrutinized some policies from various countries, states, and school districts on the use of mobile devices in science learning. Sources on policy collected from different institutions and countries provided a formidable and universal plan that may be useful in formulating strategies and studies on mobile assessment tools in education. Some studies revealed that cross-sectional and localized research studies that are limited to the relationship of specific variables such as student's sex, age, and grade level and mobile assessment tools might generate a concise image of the effectiveness of mobile devices and policy interventions.

INTRODUCTION

The perception that mobile phones use in schools is mainly a distraction is slowly diffusing out and more educators are conceding with the idea that mobile phones are useful resources in instruction. Since most learners are more interested in using mobile phones, there is a need to find ways of integrating them into the learning process. This attribute is supported by the innovations of applications (apps) such as google classroom, Canvas, Pulse, Blackboard among others which complement the Website Learning Management Systems (LMS) and support blended and online instruction. Besides, mobile phones have extra added advantages to computers in that they can take videos and photos. These can be downloaded to appropriate sites in the device such as LMS or emailed to the instructor or classmates. One more important use of mobile phones is that they are portable and good for fieldwork learning activities. Promoting personalized learning in science learning requires technology such as mobile technology that can motivate learners and enable them to study from anyplace, anywhere, and at any time. The question is, to what extent can we use mobile technology to enhance learning and demystify negative attributes associate with them?

METHODOLOGY

This study relied on a narrative literature review to gather details on the use of mobile assessment tools in learning and mainly focused on peer review articles that highlighted mobile tools in high school science education. A narrative literature review entails an objective and critical analysis of a currents study (Green et al., 2006). Currently, there are debates as to whether mobile devices can be tapped as useful tools of learning. Narrative literature reviews are a powerful study approach that can

* Douglas Ayega, University of North Texas, Denton/ USA, douglasayega@my.unt.edu

provide comprehensive knowledge and offer useful guidelines in building a comprehensive theoretical framework on topics surrounding the use of mobile assessment tools in learning.

Sources were collected from reputable educational databases such as ERIC (EBSCO), ERIC (DOE), Google Scholar, and University of North Texas Library.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Mobile devices such as personal digital assistants (PDAs), smartphones, and laptops have developed into critical learning instruments in both in and outdoor high school classroom settings. Despite the existence of an array of studies on the application of mobile gadgets in education, the specific systematic quantitative reviews regarding the influences of mobile-integrated schooling are minimal (Sung, Chang, & Liu, 2015). High school students are at a stage in their life where they are experimenting and learning new concepts and perspectives. Gradually, mobile computers are being introduced to high school environments as a form of instructional tools. Based on the reality that the internet is now a powerful phenomenon that is easily accessible and applicable in learning, many sources of mobile learning are becoming profound and interesting to learners. The enormous amount of computing portability together with content sensitivity and wireless instruments, individualized approaches of learning has offered significant prospects in both traditional and technological integrated learning.

In terms of access to computing devices, many states have executed massive one-to-one computing software to promote the integration of technology in education. This technology initially benefited middle and elementary school learners but later rolled out to high schools (Chao & Chen, 2009). High school instructors and their students have been assigned their own internet-accessible mobile devices, iPad, or Chromebooks, which they utilize to access educational material and transfer knowledge. Besides enhancing innovation and creativity in education through information technology, using mobile devices for high school students represents a convenient approach towards achieving the common objective of delivering skills and knowledge to mold the student into a respectable part of society.

The Necessity of Mobile Assessment Instruments for High School Science

In the present dynamic world that is engrossed with a multitude of technology, collecting, sharing, and disseminating information are essential components in motivating and learning. The world is rapidly and constantly changing, such that society is compelled to keep pace (Sung, Chang, & Liu, 2015). This dynamism affects learners in all aspects of their lives, including education. For instance, current educational trends, content, and news transform at such a rapid pace that it is challenging to keep pace. As such, it is critical to check and retrieve messages and news. Media such as radios, TV, desktop computers, and wired internet devices may not achieve the goal of disseminating such information quickly. One of the most powerful instruments that have altered the world of education and by association, education, is the advent of social media platforms (Christensen & Knezek, 2016). Portable and wireless devices have propagated these platforms into zones that lack accessible internet. Secondly, the conventional lecture-style of teaching is no longer interesting. Cooperative forms of learning must include innovative ways, with mobile learning assessment instruments leading the way. As outlined by Christensen & Knezek (2016), game-based learning via mobile computing tools facilitates more novel and innovative ways of gaining skills. For this reason, mobile technologies pose significant and potential opportunities for enhancing innovative learning techniques, mostly in high school science.

Science is one of the most tasking disciplines in high school education, possibly because of its demanding nature and perceived difficulty. Most students fail in the discipline because they do not possess innovative and interactive devices for making learning much fun and relevant. Evidence from research has demonstrated that in the past few years, high schools have witnessed an increased proliferation of cellphone devices in the classrooms specifically (Maphalala & Muzi, 2014). In their research, Maphalala and Muzi (2014) used a mixed-technique research design to analyze the degree to which students utilize devices in learning institutions. In one of the few different studies, they

determined that the application of e-mobile in high schools can have detrimental effects if relevant authorities do not track how students use them. For example, their study in KwaZulu-Natal and Gauteng provinces of South Africa realized that most schools did not enforce enough policies to regulate the use of cellphones within the school premises, especially in classrooms. They collected data by administered semi-structured questions, questionnaires, and focus group discussions from eight school principals, eight governing body members, eight teachers, 106 students, and eight schools. This study found that most students carry their cellular gadgets to school and proceed with them to classrooms. However, most of the schools did have concrete and functional policies that regulate phone use in the school, while these schools prohibited carrying these gadgets to school.

Similarly, other studies demonstrate that using mobile learning tools in high schools contributes to a significant range of outcomes in terms of student concentration, dedication, and learning. For example, Kuznekoff and Titsworth (2016) assessed the impact of smartphone use on overall student learning in on-session class lectures. They had participants distributed into three distinct research categories, namely, low distraction, high distraction, and control. The study required the participants to watch a video clip on their mobile phones and take notes of that particular lecture. Students participating in this study were later subjected to two different learning evaluations. The examination outcomes established that students that were not using apps on their mobile phones to collect learning material had more detailed and comprehensive notes. Of the total participants, 62% who received information using iPad collected detailed information made during the lectures and ultimately attained better grades (Kuznekoff & Titsworth, 2016). Besides, students who used mobile phones scored lower in multiple-choice questions, mostly because of distractions. However, this does not nullify the use of mobile devices in learning because some related studies have found contradictory results based on sex, age, the grade of learners, and the income of parents.

Impact of Mobile Learning Assessment Tools in Science Education: An Analysis of Evidence

Mobile learning or m-learning represents the most basic concept of mobile learning assessment because of the ease of accessing smartphones. M-learning is the application of mobile technologies for purposes of education and skills acquisition (Twum, 2017). Undoubtedly, the increased access to smartphones, internet, and applications presently gives students opportunities to augment their learning capabilities and functions. In a study, however, the researcher established that mobile phones have mixed outcomes for student learning, especially in science and technology. Twum (2017) conducted a qualitative analysis using open-ended questionnaires for 503 students and 71 instructors across three public universities. She found out that the use of smartphones has significant potential outcomes in learning, and their demand for use continues to rise. However, paradoxically, in this study, most science students did not utilize the gadgets to their optimal level in learning. Science is a technical, demanding, and complex subject of learning that is perceived to be difficult because of intricate laws, theories, hypotheses, and models that form its foundation. Because of this, m-learning technologies can be useful instruments that can enhance student learning (Nikou & Economides, 2018). However, many institutions have not fully introduced the concept into their forms of learning because of the perceived distractions and non-standardization of curricula to accommodate the use of smartphones. There is also a need to investigate negative perceptions against mobile assessment from teachers. Consequently, some of the studies published, for instance, by Keengwe (2017), Boud and Molloy (2015), and Khoo and Otrell-Cass (2017), concurred that integration of m-learning in science education possesses potential and significant outcomes when properly harnessed with strict instructor supervision. They based their argument on their studies that investigated the correlation between the use of smartphones and corresponding grades in high school science classrooms. However, they observed much distraction because most students wanted to utilize non-educational applications, which they perceived as more interesting on their mobile devices, instead of focusing on learning-related applications that they were being evaluated on. Similarly, they observed that when teachers depend too much on learning applications on mobile devices, they fail to impart guided one-on-one learning that the students require. For example, in a biology laboratory session, students need direct guidance on hazardous chemicals and dangerous animals.

Today, most middle school and high school authorities are constantly battling the proliferation of mobile gadgets in school's vis-a-vis, achieving learning outcomes. On the flip side, students find creative ways of concealing these devices, surf the internet, and share material on social media while the instructor is in session (Sung, Chang, & Liu, 2015; Rung, Warnke, & Mattheos, 2014). The outcome is that students fail or perform dismally in the class. One of the most recent studies by the University of Nebraska in Lincoln established that more high school students spend their class time using smartphones more than ever (Machmud, 2018). This study found that the students spend approximately 20 percent of their classroom time using their devices at the rate of at least 11 times in one day. Roughly 30 percent of students in this study argued that they would utilize their mobile devices devoid of distractions from learning and understand the lesson content. Further, over 25 percent of the students in the study contended that it is their individual choice whether to utilize mobile gadgets or not, even with strict instructions not to do so. It is, therefore, essential to point out to learners the negative impacts associated with the inappropriate use of these devices during preparation, especially if they are part of the learning process.

The Use of Mobile Learning for Science

The application of mobile assessment instruments for science education can be either web-based applications or native applications. Native based applications are inbuilt within the mobile operating systems (MOS). They utilize their specific code library to enable access to the gadget's hardware devices, for example, a global positioning system (GPS), memory, and the camera (El-Hussein, M., & Cronje, 2010; Roth, Ogrin, & Bernhard Schmitz, 2016). On its part, a web-based mobile application can be within the host system, with the mobile gadget's browser being able to access the features that it offers. Because of the need for security and authorized access to m-learning materials, various modules characterize this technology. The modules include registration, details of login, selection of the subject, department selection, and other specific details as customized by the institution. Then, the student receives a username and private password that they can utilize to access learning material from the portal. When high school students obtain authentication and the right to information, they are good to start using them.

M-learning in high school science classes is useful in various ways. Several studies have analyzed the efficacy and failures of mobile instructions in science. Cahyana, Paristiowati, Savitri (2017), and Hasyrin (2017) carried out one such study to advance and comprehend the impact of the mobile-founded game-based instructions among high school students in different schools in Jakarta. This study relied on a quasi-experiment approach whereby manipulation of one variable is done without random assignment of conditions to participants. In this study, the learning process applied expert validated M-GBL media. The control utilized conventional learning devoid of the internet or mobile devices. The results indicated that M-GBL media had a constructive impact on the students in biochemistry learning classes when administered to the students who have relatively high autonomy in learning. This outcome justifies that the use of learning devices as learning media can positively enhance grades and concentration in science classes.

Similarly, the same study by Machmudmn (2018), suggested that traits of the effective utilization of M-GBL media in high school student learning should incorporate Random Access Memory (RAM) and mobile devices as multimedia tools of instruction with the traditional printed materials. Therefore, the use of RAM and mobile-based education can be appropriate alternatives to conventional learning to enhance learning because they are locally accessible at any time and any location.

Mobile-based science-learning applications enhance intrinsic motivation drive because they contain electronic games that summarize the lesson's contents, illicit fun, and facilitate self-learning. According to Danasingh (2017), self-learning has proven to be a critical player in enhancing students' knowledge of lessons, especially in sciences. A mobile learning environment with the appropriate monitoring enables students to grasp more understanding even without the teacher's guidance.

Learning management tools in education available mobile gadgets are expanding at an unprecedented rate to complement their access through the websites. Teachers can upload instructional material to cloud-based apps or learning management tools such as Google Classroom, Canvas, or Blackboard.

These mobile apps offer instant notifications to learners whenever the instructor updates any information such as grade updates, assignment due, and emails. Mobile applications address problems such as student absence since the students can access content using m-learning applications and download them even when there is the nonexistence of the internet using data bundles. They can submit their assignments from wherever they are.

Policy Enhancement on M-learning

The fundamental processes of accessing and utilizing technology are generally well established in most of the country's high schools and across other spheres of education. This may include iPads, Chromebooks, and desktop computers. Some institutions have shifted their focus to the students' mobile gadgets as useful resources of learning devoid other factors such as security, issues regarding protocol, network coverage, and bandwidth difficulties (Chao & Chen, 2009; Sun & Looi, 2016). There is, therefore, the need to address these factors by enacting relevant policies so that we can utilize the gadgets as useful learning resources. There are constant issues regarding a digital divide as institutions in different states re-supply their mobile learning equipment in varying proportions, durations, and volumes. Despite the inconsistency, research has demonstrated that America has a profound wave of mobile education functions. However, the trend in science education, unlike reading and mathematics, is mostly narrowly focused on and does not include expanded functionalities and coverage.

Educational stakeholders, including policymakers, educators, instructors, students, and parents, must embrace technology in science education, albeit the ramifications associated with them. Enforcement of m-learning in science learning should focus on a one-to-one basis based on research done on target populations. This is because, in the U.S, the integration of technology to provide science education in high schools is evident. However, the process of implementing these processes if done in a unified or wholesome manner without consideration of specific factors reflected by schools. As stated by Wrabel et al. (2016) and Weiss and May (2012), the federal government enacted the Elementary and Secondary Education Act in 2001 to enforce the integration of technology in K-12 education in mathematics, special education, and sciences. This act, together with the law on "No Child is Left Behind," promotes accountability systems specified by respective States and students' achievement (Porter, Linn, & Trimble, 2005). The fundamental question of these acts is whether they were realized in research findings on a specific target population that addressed one to one factor.

Despite the good intentions that the government had for integrating technology into high school education, the regulations for implementation only focused on basic skills in math, reading, and writing. Other subjects, such as physics, biology, and chemistry, received minimal attention. Test grades in humanities and science in high schools were not part of the calculation used to determine student's achievement. The No Child Left Behind (NCLB) proficiency measures that gauge the level of deployment of technology in learning has not specified a clear guideline on how to account for the actual use of m-Learning in high schools. With the rapid emergence of mobile devices and technological advancements in schools, these laws and policies should not overlook their impacts of m-learning on student achievements in science subjects.

Studies on M-learning

Mixed-Method Approach

Most investigations on m-learning in science subjects lack a detailed and in-depth examination of the entire learning process (Sharples et al., 2014; Shih, Chuang, & Hwang, 2010). Sharples et al. (2014) adopted mixed methods of research to analyze high school students' engagement and interaction with mobile devices in classes. One of the key findings from this study is that student participation in performing science using m-learning activities depend on grade levels, subject, teacher feedback, and type of mobile instrument. The outcomes revealed the issues affecting student's participation in mobile science education and the challenges in the mobile-integrated science curriculum. Potentially, the results informed the curriculum designers and implementers using mobile technologies to rethink some of the strategies in m-learning. They suggested that it is not only enough to introduce mobile

technologies into classrooms; instead, it is also appropriate to introduce training programs for professional educators to participate in the process of conception, modeling, and execution of mobile technology programs to augment learning. Likewise, these studies should incorporate the perception of instructors and their experiences with m-learning activities in a variety of subjects.

Diversion from the Traditional Approach of Learning

With the advancement of mobile technology, it is possible to make science learning portable. A study by Martin and Ertzberger (2013) and Zydney and Warner (2016) observed that mobile learning instruments facilitate science learning in a controlled, monitored, and planned environments. Sharples et al. (2009) stated that mobile learning instruments pose novel techniques that can be used to extend the learning process beyond the conventional brick and mortar classrooms. Mobile learning contributes to increased participation in educational conversations, sharing of ideas, concepts, and as a way of submitting information, including tests and other useful learning information. High school students will be able to examine the real-world science experience on their hands and demonstrate scientific knowledge and principles outside the classroom and laboratory context. Similarly, students will be able to access social networks. Social networks will open many opportunities for them to attain social skills, competencies, and knowledge related to learning science themes.

Improvements on the Nontraditional Approach

It is necessary to introduce a more finely tuned analysis that offers a comprehensive report of how m-learning instruments align with the students' daily lives. These experiences should define the applications, failures, as well as opportunities for improvement (Chou, Block, & Jesness, 2012; Harmon, 2012). Additionally, there is a need for collaborative assessment guidelines associated with m-learning instruments in different fields of science. Song, Wong, and Looi (2012) suggested an objective-based strategy to design an appropriate m-learning curriculum intended to instruct students through an individualized inquiry learning approach. Findings demonstrated that m-learning instruments assisted students to participate in deliberations with greater enthusiasm, interpret topics, share, and reflect following their inquiry. The procedure was found to be useful in developing the learners' self-directed learning and scientific knowledge skills.

Example of M-learning Platform and Potential Outcomes

Ahmed (2013) presented an m-learning platform known as Think Learn to augment students' abductive skill inquiry in examinations, exploration, explanation, and selection. The studies demonstrated that mobile learning instruments could contribute to mediation and active roles in instructing science topics both within and beyond the classroom. Hence, once the stakeholders have succeeded in making suitable pedagogical approaches, for instance, using inquiry-based principles, then there is considerable potential for enhancing high school students' knowledge, competences, attitudes, and skills in science. Patterns and trends in educational techniques will probably not only assist classroom instructions in high school education, but might also enhance the advancement of problem-solving, high-level skills, communication, and creativity among the students. However, despite the projected benefits of applying mobile learning assessment tools for enhanced computer user-friendliness, teaching styles, portability, and scholarly performance, researchers have found mixed outcomes regarding the influences of mobile computing devices in education (Christensen & Knezek, 2016; Sung, Chang, & Liu, 2015). Similarly, some researchers have studied fundamental aspects of utilizing mobile computing gadgets and their subsequent effectiveness. The few published studies demonstrated that there is a positive influence on student learning. For instance, a publication by Chao and Chen (2009) observed that the application of laptop programs boosted activities that enhance higher-level memory and reasoning and transform classroom teaching and instructional techniques. Powell and Mason (2013) revealed that students who used laptops more regularly took notes and finished their assignments on time. They reviewed thirty analyses that sought to determine the utilization of wireless connectivity via laptops and other mobile computing devices. The overall finding was that the more the students utilized the connectivity devices, the more they accomplished tasks as required. Some of these learning websites have been transformed and availed in portable devices such as iPad, mobile phones, and Chromebooks in the form of apps. Marfisi-Schottman and

George (2014) and Crompton et al. (2016) carried out studies on m-learning platforms, albeit with different findings and techniques. Marfisi-Schottman and George (2014) contend that it is essential to train teachers regarding how to integrate mobile learning platforms. The study applies a descriptive approach, where the researchers analyze the technical challenges that instructors might experience, as well as ways of improving them and making the teachers the leaders of the entire e-learning process. In particular, this study demonstrated that m-learning games play a vital role in student learning as opposed to standard apps.

General-purpose programs such as presentation software, web browsers, and word processors are the most used resources in learning. Most of the schools employing one-on-one mobile computing software such as personal digital assistants, mobile devices, and tablets, registered a considerable improvement in collaborative learning and active student engagement among students (Alvarez, Alarcon, & Nussbaum, 2011). Besides that, learners who use their mobile computing devices for learning, typing, browsing, taking tests, doing homework, and making presentations had better prospects of gaining new skills. Moreover, instructors make more progress and changes to their modes of instruction when they have opportunities for using mobile computing devices (Christensen & Knezek, 2016). The students who engaged in one-to-one initiatives also showed deeper engagement with the material they were being instructed on as compared to the rest of the control group. Based on these findings, it is prudent to say that mobile devices can be useful pedagogical tools of learning in enhancing collaborative learning and promoting student engagement and participation.

The changing perceptions of M-Learning.

There are broad discussions that entail the ubiquitous learning and attributes of mobile computing. Ubiquitous or mobile learning has been on the upward trend since 2008 when it became popular (Powell & Mason, 2013). However, in the past, researchers have mostly covered studies on institutions of higher learning, with few research studies done on high school and middle schools. The studies mainly focused on a few spheres of education, engineering, language, arts, and information technology or in specific topics such as anatomy, physiology, and genetics. However, in the present world, the narrative has changed; individuals are embracing mobile technology as a way of life. Mobile computing has become an integral part of life to the degree that it applies to all areas, with education being one of the standout domains. Today, most students in high schools have unlimited access to the internet and have smartphones, which enable them to communicate freely and share information. Unlike the past, many school administrations now permit the application of mobile technological devices on their school premises. They have even accepted various applications as forms of instructing their students, and mobile phones have become a supplement and reinforcement instrument used to strengthen learner engagement and stimulate motivation (Sung, Chang, & Liu, 2015). Therefore, mobile computing devices constitute a critical content and instructional delivery instrument.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The assorted studies portray several perspectives on the influence of mobile learning assessment instruments in high school science. Whereas the reviews are not consistent or do not show concurring information, it is evident that mobile technologies have significant effects on science education when effectively utilized. The US education system has not holistically implemented a curriculum that ensures uniform implementation of m-learning standards for the schools. Similarly, the differences in different State's application of m-learning standards are detrimental to advancing mobile learning.

On the flip side, some studies have depicted that the utilization of m-learning technologies contributes to lower grades, distractions, and a lack of one-to-one practical guidance. However, these various merits result from confounding factors such as the location of school (urban or rural), learner's socio-economical background, age, and grade level. Despite the setbacks, mobile learning instruments offer significant opportunities for self-directed learning, improvement of student attention in and outside the classroom, and inquiry-based learning. Therefore, appropriate integration of mobile learning assessment tools in high school science is vital.

Future Studies

Noticeably, there are no research approaches that have been of focus to justify a specific outcome on m-learning. Studies in this field range from qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods, which fail to yield to a universal rational conclusion. Correlations of most of the reviews are done between areas in far-flung places that experience unrelated variables. There is a need to enumerate a variety of studies that focus on the same population or location. It would also be prudent to conduct empirical research and replications that focus on specific themes over a period. For example, formal cross-sectional research on the topic would be essential. A more localized study would be appropriate to generate a concise image to enable policy interventions.

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